

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (AJMRI)

ISSN: 2158-8155 (ONLINE), 2832-4854 (PRINT)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 4 (2022)

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PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

The Mediating Effect of Teaching Effectiveness on the Relationship Between Passion and Commitment Among Public Elementary School Teachers

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Article Information

Received: September 09, 2022

Accepted: September 23, 2022

Published: September 27, 2022

Keywords

Commitment, Educational Management, Mediating Effect, Passion, Philippines, Teaching Effectiveness

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the mediating effect of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between passion and commitment among 300 teachers in the Division of Davao del Sur. This study employed a non-experimental design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique. The statistical tools used were mean Pearson r and path analysis using SPSS AMOS. Research instruments on passion, commitment, and teaching effectiveness were validated and used as data sources. Using Pearson r , the results revealed a significant relationship between passion and commitment, passion and Teaching effectiveness, and teaching effectiveness and commitment. Utilizing path analysis, the study's results showed no mediation of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between passion and commitment. Consequently, the findings of this study contended that teaching effectiveness as mediating variable carries no influence on passion and commitment.

INTRODUCTION

Commitment to Teaching is a critical aspect of helping pupils reach their goals. In addition, one of the essential components of effective Teaching is instructor commitment (Lim & Thien, 2020; McInerney et al., 2015). Consequently, educators who are highly committed to making a difference in their student's learning and accomplishments have the potential to do so. On the other hand, when teachers do not work/perform as expected by management, the result harms students. Everyone is concerned about the quality of students in terms of competency and knowledge from such teachers. It is also one of the reasons why, although it is very prevalent, many parents today are hesitant to enroll their children in public schools (Shafiq & Akram Rana, 2016). According to Atun (2017), teacher commitment comes from within and makes teachers spend more time and energy staying involved in the school. This desire to promote the school builds an emotional tie between teachers and the institution, which motivates teachers to seek out techniques to improve their Teaching and create a pleasant learning environment in which students can reach their goals. Thus, committed are lifelong learners who are also committed to education. This article will examine a few of the most important aspects of being a passionate teacher.

Although there is extensive literature on passion, it is somewhat unexplored in the field of education. Furthermore, while a growing body of literature shows a significant link between teacher commitment and the highly personal characteristic of passion for Teaching, no research has been done on the mediating effect of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between passion

and commitment. Furthermore, committed teachers are recognized for their pupils' success. Teachers are passionate about what they do, develop an instructional setting that is productive, and help students reach their full potential (Castillo et al., 2017; Cheasakul & Varma, 2016; Prates et al., 2019). Because passion is a precursor to creativity, educators who are driven by it are better able to think on their feet and rapidly generate novel ideas. Passionate educators are committed and dedicated to their schools, and the positive educational outcomes that result from this commitment and dedication are a direct result of this passion. Thus, to address the aforementioned theoretical gaps, the research sought to establish the relationship between passion and commitment, passion and Teaching effectiveness, teaching effectiveness and commitment, and the mediating effect of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between passion and commitment.

The researcher, aware of the significance of studies on teachers' commitment, conducted a comprehensive assessment of the relevant literature in search of potential characteristics. Passion was the first variable considered to be appropriate. Passion is essential since it motivates and inspires the teachers. (Martin et al., 2014). Teachers are zealous around their careers and committed to their pupils' erudition, which severely influences their growth (Zhang et al., 2016). Another variable that caught the attention of the researcher is teaching effectiveness. One of the most important aspects of a student's life is their ability to learn well. It can purify and change the behavior of students. Effective teachers always assist their pupils in establishing good physical and mental health. They are constantly developing pupils to develop

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their fundamental abilities, intellectual processes, healthy habits, scientific temperament, positive attitudes, value orientation, value judgment, and the ability to adjust to a constantly shifting psychosocial environment (Hawkins et al., 2013). Nevertheless, the researcher is interested in learning how the efficiency of Teaching moderates the teacher's passion's effect on their commitment.

In light of the information presented above, the researcher developed an interest in determining whether or not teaching effectiveness will mediate the relationship between the passion and commitment of teachers. As a result, this study has the potential to generate new knowledge that can make a significant contribution to the field of education.

Research Objectives

The primary focus of this investigation is to discover the mediating effect of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between passion and commitment among public elementary school's teachers.

Specifically, the following objectives were formulated:

1. To describe the level of passion among public elementary school teachers in terms of
 - 1.1 harmonious passion; and
 - 1.2 obsessive passion.
2. To ascertain the level of commitment among public elementary school teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 commitment to student;
 - 2.2 commitment to Teaching;
 - 2.3 commitment to school; and
 - 2.4 commitment to profession
3. To measure the level of teaching effectiveness among public elementary school teachers.
4. To determine the significance of the relationship between:
 - 4.1 passion and commitment;
 - 4.2 passion and teaching effectiveness; and
 - 4.3 teaching effectiveness and commitment.
5. To determine the significance of mediation of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between passion and commitment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study focused on the independent variable is passion with the indicators such as passion criteria, harmonious passion and obsessive passion (Zhao et. al, 2015). The dependent variable is commitment with the indicators such as commitment to a student; commitment to Teaching; commitment to school; and commitment to profession (Thien et. al, 2014). And, the mediating variable is teaching effectiveness (Barnes, 2000).

Passion

Teachers passionate about their subjects are noted for their enthusiasm, intellectual emotion, emotional energy, and commitment. When engaging with pupils, they have a sense of identity and believe they can make a difference

in their learning and achievement. As a result, a love of Teaching contributes to a greater understanding and improvement of the teaching profession, as well as new insights into the work and life of teachers. Instructors' commitment is associated with their sense of professional emotional identity, and teachers' commitment is associated with their professional emotional identity. The best teaching approaches come from a blend of emotional and intellectual capacities (Adetunji, 2018; Castillo et al., 2017; Cheasakul & Varma, 2016; Prates et al., 2019).

It was pointed out, however, that taking passion is not enough. The teacher's enthusiasm must be sustained, which may happen when they improve or increase their job. It was claimed that instructors must be lifelong learners if they want to keep their passion for Teaching. Teachers should keep updated on new research, theories, and breakthroughs in their fields. Teachers maintain their enthusiasm for their subjects by continuing to learn. Their confidence allows them to express their enthusiasm for their subject with coworkers and students (Benekos, 2016; Khan, 2020; Kim, 2017; Owen, 2016).

Passion, commitment, flexibility, and efficacy are also cultivated and perpetuated through professional discussion and the practicing community's active participation. Several authors describe the maintenance of teaching passion as being linked to and between teacher dedication and resilience, in that passionate teachers are more likely to resurface in difficult situations and shifting contexts. This is because Teaching is founded on a passion that must be preserved, nurtured, developed, and perpetuated to make a difference in students' learning lives and achievements. Though, early enthusiasm may wane due to factors such as teacher age and maintaining it (Robson, 2020; Mensah, 2019; Vallerand, 2016; Zhang, 2019).

One factor that measures passion is the harmonious passion. Harmonious passions, it was thought, are cultivated in situations that promote autonomy and intrinsic needs. Individuals in autonomous environments can explore and pick whatever activities are meaningful to them. Autonomous situations, on the other hand, can promote intrinsic drive. Intrinsically motivated people, for example, pursue goals or rewards based on their own innate needs and participate in activities just for enjoyment and interest they give. In this situation, an individual may build a balanced enthusiasm for an activity based on its fun and satisfaction (Greenberger, 2016; Moe, 2016; Ruiz-Alfonso & Leon, 2019; Yeh & Chu, 2018).

In addition to this, several researchers mentioned that having passions in harmony with one another is advantageous to one's mental health. It was also believed that having harmonious passions contributed to favorable effects during and after activity involvement. It has also been established that people whose passions are in harmony experience higher levels of focus when they are involved in their activity (Appu & Sia, 2017; Kim & Connelly, 2019; Spehar et al., 2016; Yukhymenko-Lescroart & Sharma, 2019; Yukhymenko-Lescroart &

Sharma, 2019);

Generally, people with a harmonic passion should be able to focus on the activity at hand entirely and have favorable consequences during and after task engagement (e.g., flow, pleasant effect, and concentration) (e.g., satisfaction, general positive affect). As a result, there should be little or no conflict between the person's intense activity and the rest of their daily activities. Finally, with harmonic passion, the individual is in charge of the action and can choose when and when not to engage in it. People who have a harmonious passion can decide not to participate in the activity on a given day if necessary or even to end their involvement with the movement if they determine it has become a constant negative aspect in their lives. Thus, behavioral involvement in a passionate activity might be viewed as adaptable (Curran et al., 2015; Dalla Rosa & Vianello, 2020; Gao & Jiang, 2019; Peng et al., 2020).

Obsessive passion, on the other hand, is the consequence of a controlled integration of the action into one's identity. Internalization occurs as a result of intrapersonal and interpersonal pressure, either because certain contingencies are associated with the activity, such as feelings of social acceptance or self-esteem, or because the sense of excitement derived from activity engagement becomes uncontrollable (Ruiz-Alfonso & Leon, 2017; Valler et al., 2020; Weiss et al., 2017; Yeh & Chu, 2018). People with an obsessive interest may have an overpowering need to participate in the activity they see as significant and delightful. The person's zeal for the action takes over. They cannot help but engage in vigorous exercise, leading to inflexible perseverance. While such strict persistence may occasionally result in specific benefits (e.g., an improvement in the activity over time), it may also result in some costs, potentially resulting in less-than-optimal functioning within the boundaries of the passionate action due to the lack of flexibility that it requires (Bouizegarene et al., 2018; Burke et al., 2015b; Fisher et al., 2018; Stroe et al., 2018).

When a person is stopped from partaking in an activity that they have an obsessive passion for, there is a good chance that it will have a harmful effect. It is because the activity dominates the person with obsessive passion. It is physically hard to completely withdraw from one's thoughts regarding the movement of passion because of the internal demand to participate in the activity. Therefore, the individual will be distracted when working on other things since they will not be able to engage in the movement that brings them the most joy.

The individual will suffer feelings of frustration and upset as a result of their inability to participate in the training that they are enthusiastic about, as well as their inability to derive pleasure from the activities that are competing with it (Booth, 2018; Burke et al., 2015c; Lu, 2019; Owen, 2015).

Corollary to this, having a strong passion can make one's job enjoyable. Employees are willing to partake in whatever activities in their job when their passion is high. Thus, leaders must watch over employees' passion in

an organization. In this way, low-performing employees can be given interventions. Monitoring employees' performance is one good way of maintaining employees' passion for working hard for the betterment of an organization.

Commitment

Commitment is an inside strength that drives instructors to commit more of one's time and effort to maintain their involvement in the schools in which they work. This readiness to promote the school generates an expressive connection between instructors and the school, which eventually encourages educators to look for methods to strengthen the teaching job and produce a productive setting for academic endeavors to assist students in achieving their goals. Dedication to one's profession is one of the most important considerations that can influence the academic achievement of one's pupils (Chesnut & Burley, 2015; Heinz, 2015; Hong et al., 2018; Moses et al., 2017).

Also, it was stated that a sincere dedication to the profession of Teaching is the best way to advance one's career in that field. Because of their dedication to the profession, instructors have the responsibility to investigate and experiment with ever-evolving new methods of instruction to enrich their pupils' educational experiences. Teachers committed to their pupils can give students new teaching tactics, which may lead to improved academic performance (Altun, 2017; Noddings & Brooks, 2016; Han et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2019).

In addition, teachers dedicated to their work can foster zealous students by encouraging their pupils to participate in extracurricular activities. Commitment on the part of teachers is crucial to delivering high-quality instruction. It involves a dedication to the students, school, the continuation of their careers, the expansion of their professional knowledge bases, and the teaching profession. Teachers committed to their kids enjoy working with their students and are concerned about how their students grow. These educators exert a significant amount of effort to maximize the effectiveness of Teaching and learning by utilizing various methods (Altun, 2017; Crosswell & Elliott, 2004; González et al., 2018; Yeap et al., 2020).

Furthermore, a dedication to the teaching profession enables educators to adapt their pedagogical strategies to assist in better learning in the classroom. Improved work performance is a vital requirement for creating a productive learning environment for students in which students are actively engaged in their educational pursuits. Additionally, dedicated instructors develop a sense of allegiance to the institution in which they are employed. They are willing to put in a significant amount of effort on behalf of the institution. All of these factors impact the academic success of students (Bansal, 2016; Lin et al., 2020; Ostad et al., 2019; Margaritoiu, 2015). They also assist students in achieving their educational objectives.

Interacting with pupils and monitoring students' learning

development is salient to teachers committed to Teaching. These educators deeply grapple with the challenge of maximizing teaching and learning effectiveness by utilizing various pedagogical methodologies. Being a good educator without passion for what one does is impossible. Educators that have a solid dedication to their profession are passionate about their work. In addition to this, they have a healthy regard for their pupils. Notably, they cultivate solid relationships with their pupils, which are the hallmark of excellent educators (Akter et al., 2019; Marshall, 2015; Sharma, 2015; Zhang, 2015).

In most cases, the devotion of the teaching staff is at the center of outstanding education. It has an impact on advancing the teaching profession and work performance, academic achievement, and the success of students. Teachers who are committed to their students are always looking for new methods of instruction that will aid their students in better comprehending the material (Ford et al., 2017); (Lim & Thien, 2020; McInerney et al., 2015; Shafiq & Akram Rana, 2016).

Furthermore, it was stated that this moral obligation manifests as a result of socialization within a society or an organization. In either scenario, the policy is founded on the principle of reciprocity; to put it another way, if an employee is given a perk, either they or the company have a moral obligation to extend the same courtesy to other members of the organization. After all, the committed employee of the norm believes that continuing to be a part of the organization is the morally correct thing to do, regardless of how much status advancement or satisfaction the organization has provided them with over the years (Bansal, 2016; Lin et al., 2020; Ostad et al., 2019; Margarițoiu, 2015) (Bansal, 2016; Lin et al., 2020; Ostad et al., 2019; Margarițoiu, 2015).

Consequently, commitment to any affiliated organization, department, and the company is beneficial to attain success and compelling rendering of service, which can motivate others to work hard. This variable plays a vital part in the lives of teachers in the context of the instruction and education method carried out in the education sector, which affects students' learning. Committed teachers can inspire pupils to learn, work with fellow teachers, and innovate teaching techniques, approaches and strategies— additionally, teachers with high commitment to teaching work zealously, as enumerated earlier. Thus, committed teachers are goal-oriented people as the catalyst of change and fighters in combating illiteracy worldwide.

Teaching Effectiveness

Teaching effectiveness is used generically to refer to the characteristics, competencies, and behaviors at all educational levels that enable students to achieve desired objectives. It was asserted that teaching effectiveness is synonymous with individual teacher performance and that teaching effectiveness includes knowledge, attitudes, and performance. Teaching effectiveness is critical because each teacher's efficacy is the lifeblood of any educational institution. Teacher qualities, in particular, are one of

the aspects that determine teachers' overall efficacy. Teacher characteristics are related to and influence how instructors conduct their job (Boring et al., 2016; Paolini, 2015; Steinert et al., 2016; Uttl et al., 2017). Effective instructors are individuals who succeed in achieving the objectives, either those they have set for themselves or those that others have set for them.

They help their pupils achieve specific learning objectives and larger ones such as problem-solving, critical thinking, collaborative work, and being productive citizens. Furthermore, the work of effective teachers is felt well beyond the confines of the classroom. Their kids acquire a love of study and belief in themselves that will remain with them throughout the rest of their life. It must also be remembered that the quality of a teacher can create a difference in a student's learning growth for an entire year in a single year (Lee & Li, 2015; Liu et al., 2019; Polikoff, 2015; Rahimi & Karkami, 2015).

Because competent teachers are required, teachers must be evaluated in order for them to be effective. Evaluating teachers' performance in educational institutions is equivalent to evaluating students' learning; hence assessing teaching effectiveness in education is critical. Evaluations are regarded as significant since they help determine performance and effectiveness. Specific measures are required to discover specific talents and habits that individual teachers can develop (Hassan et al., 2015; McClain et al., 2018; Sandilos et al., 2019; Xu & Chen, 2016).

It should be mentioned, however, that evaluating teaching effectiveness has proven difficult, partly due to the continuous argument over what a good teacher is and does. Looking at teaching efficacy from students' perspectives is one way to shed light on this enigma. It was agreed that student evaluations should be incorporated into the teacher assessment process. Such acknowledgment is based on the assumption that students are direct consumers of the services offered by instructors and are thus in a strong position to assess and evaluate the work of their teachers (Husain et al., 2015; Moraros et al., 2015; Sellnow-Richmond et al., 2020; Zakaria et al., 2019).

Students have a lot to say about their educational experiences, and they may play an active part in improving teaching quality and learning. As a result, student perspectives are precious. Student ratings are a critical source of evidence of teaching success for both formative and summative choices, and student evaluations are an essential component of any teacher assessment system (Goldhaber et al., 2017; Kini & Podolsky, 2016; Nikoopour & Esfandiari, 2017; Polat & Cepik, 2016).

Furthermore, studies agree that the teachers at a student's school are one of the essential factors in determining not only their future academic achievement but also the results of their lives. As a direct consequence of this, there has been a primary focus placed on enhancing teachers' effectiveness to improve students' learning. Students who highly successful teachers instructed had a greater chance of going to college, earning more money,

residing in communities with higher incomes, saving more money for retirement, and having fewer children while they were still in their teenage years. Researchers and policymakers need to comprehensively understand the factors that contribute to a teacher's effectiveness since a highly effective teacher can considerably enhance the lives of their students (Chetty et al., 2014; Rivkin et al., 2005; Rockoff, 2004).

However, good Teaching should be concerned with more than only the academic aims of students. Teachers' effectiveness should include consideration of their pupils' aspirations. Students arrive to class from a variety of backgrounds and with a variety of perspectives apart from academics, which a competent teacher should consider. An effective teacher will always maximize and make appropriate use of instructional time. A teacher who wastes time in class discussing trivial matters is ineffective (Stronge et al., 2011).

Besides, a great teacher must have high expectations for learning. A teacher with low expectations for their pupils' ability to acquire a topic will be unconcerned if, at the end of the lesson, the pupils do not realize the significance of the idea. If, on the other hand, the instructor had set a high standard for students' grasp of the concept and the students did not understand it at the end of the class, the teacher should be moved to investigate the cause and maybe re-teach the idea to increase understanding (Boring et al., 2016; Carpenter et al., 2020; Steinert et al., 2016; Uttl et al., 2017).

As a result, assessment and feedback are critical to students' learning. Feedback has been constructive in Teaching and learning since it promotes student learning. Every good teacher should understand how, when, and what type of assessment and feedback is required for the class. Teachers use several sorts of evaluation; regardless of the form, assessment activities consume a significant amount of teacher time and play a vital role in teachers' and students' lives (Jensen et al., 2019; Miguel et al., 2019; Wieman, 2019). Furthermore, a successful educator will always engage well with students both within and outside the classroom, which is critical to students' learning. Interaction between teacher and student is critical in school, and good teachers should provide maximum interaction to improve classroom-based education and study. According to one study, one of the reasons Physics students do not perform well academically is a lack of proper connection between teacher and student. The interaction/relationship between the teacher and the student in a specific subject determines student interest and achievement. Creating strong classroom cultures with healthy relationships helps students use their energies and ambitions to achieve their goals (Liu et al., 2019; Okoli, 2017; Sandilos et al., 2019; Xu & Chen, 2016).

Indeed, most students learn best in a setting where they can freely express themselves, which could be when they are free with the teacher. Several authors believed that learning takes place best in an environment that fosters positive interpersonal relationships and exchanges, as

well as one in which learners feel valued, acknowledged, esteemed, and respected. Pupils who have a deep connection that is supportive with their instructor are more involved and effort in class, have more remarkable perseverance in the face of adversity and cope better with stress (Baliyan & Moorad, 2018; Donnelly-Sallee, 2018; Hanson et al., 2018; Mantzicopoulos et al., 2018).

Aside from the above-listed aspects of teacher success, others that are very significant in determining instructor effectiveness are motivation, content understanding, and students' assignments. Many scientific students who have lost interest in the course, which could be owing to the abstract nature of the subject matter or teachers' poor teaching strategies, may find that motivation can serve as a spark to reignite their interest in the course. According to the findings of one study, youngsters' learning is significantly aided by their level of motivation. The result is usually unfavorable in situations lacking this motivation due to inadequate education (Boonsem & Chaonsupmanee, 2020; Cohen et al., 2020; McClain et al., 2018; Santini et al., 2018).

Teacher efficacy in the classroom is critical, and pupils' academic performance suffers when an instructor is ineffective in the schoolroom. The value of teacher efficacy should not be underestimated, which is why unqualified hiring teachers in schools is inappropriate. Any competent teacher understands the value of homework in Teaching and learning and ensures that it is assigned regularly. Homework is acknowledged as a predictor of successful schools and pupils. The teacher should create more effective and encouraging homework, allowing low-ability kids to complete it on time (Polat & Cepik, 2016; Sahu et al., 2018; Sellnow-Richmond et al., 2020).

Furthermore, according to research findings, teacher self-efficacy is a vital variable in teacher effectiveness that is consistently associated with teacher behaviors and student results. Some people believe that teachers with low self-efficacy cannot be effective. At the same time, some authors argue that high-efficacy teachers are more likely to create higher student outcomes because they are more persistent in assisting students with challenges. According to studies, teachers with a high degree of confidence in their abilities in their capacity to teach can yield more incredible student accomplishments in various academic areas (Baroody, 2017; Newman et al., 2016).

Provided reviews of teaching effectiveness discussed herein are pivotal in the continuous evaluation of teaching performance of teachers whether in private or public schools. Teaching effectiveness means absorbing lessons in the learners' minds and is tantamount to student learning. Committed teachers are experts in teaching lessons and competencies in their respective class. In Addendum, committed teachers are responsible for the learning gains obtained by the learners. They see to it that students have learned the lesson; and performed excellently in giving interventions to succor struggling learners in terms of reading, numeracy skills, solving problems, answering WH questions etc.

METHODOLOGY

The primary section of the survey is devoted to the subject of the passion teachers have for their work, and it includes indicators such as harmonious passion and obsessive passion. The study that served as the basis for the instrument later used and modified is: (Zhao et al., 2015). This part has 6 items per indicator.

The second part of the questionnaire is utilized to evaluate the level of commitment selected for use, and subsequent research led to its modification (Thien et al., 2014). There were three kinds of indicators on this variable, and each hand was made up of six items. The research conducted by Barness was used as a basis for the third set of questionnaires, which were then changed (1998).

The Likert scales, which have five points, were utilized for the different factors in the study. According to Santos (2007), in order to use the Likert Scale, one must first check a box or leave a blank in answer to many questions addressing an object, a stimulus, and an attitude. It is common practice to immediately use the numbers received from a rating scale as measures by doing calculations such as computing averages or, more generally speaking, any

arithmetic operations.

Lastly, this survey questionnaire was pretested to 40 respondents from different schools to test the reliability of the modified questionnaire. The purpose of pre-testing is to ensure that questions are effective in eliciting the intended responses and that those who are likely to reply to them understand the questions (Hilton, 2015). Hence, results indicated an overall acceptable rating of 0.82 Cronbach alpha .826 in passion, 0.708 in commitment, and 0.929 in teaching effectiveness. SPSS AMOS used to analyse the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Passion

Shown in Table 1 is the level of Passion. The standard deviation was less than 1.00 meaning there is uniformity among respondents. The overall mean score was 4.17 labeled as high. Distinctively, the level of passion of teachers on the following indicators were as follows: passion criteria got a mean of 4.53 described as very high, harmonious passion has a mean of 4.44 with a descriptive level of very high, and obsessive passion has a mean of 3.54 characterized as high.

Table 1: Level of Passion

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Passion Criteria	0.40	4.53	Very High
Harmonious Passion	0.44	4.44	Very High
Obsessive Passion	0.72	3.54	High
Overall	0.40	4.17	High

Data revealed that the teachers had manifested excellent passion in terms of passion criteria which indicates that teachers were devoted in Teaching by means of coaching and mentoring learners effectively. Also, the statistics showed that passion in terms of harmonious passion

teachers had displayed an outstanding job which shows that teachers know how to be with learners and cater their needs especially in the teaching and learning process. Table 2 shows the results of the level of commitment of public elementary schools in Davao del Sur. The overall

Table 2: Level of Commitment

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Commitment to Students	0.49	4.43	Very High
Commitment to Teaching	0.45	4.52	Very High
Commitment to School	0.54	4.19	High
Commitment to Profession	0.44	4.33	Very High
Overall	0.29	3.92	High

mean score was 3.92, labeled as high. Mainly, the level of responsibility on the following indicators was as follows: commitment to students has a mean of 4.43 with an interpretation of very high, commitment to Teaching has a mean of 4.52 labeled as very high, commitment to school has a mean of 4.19 characterized as high, and commitment to the profession has a mean of 4.33 described as very high. Furthermore, it was observed that commitment to students, Teaching, and profession obtained a very high rating, indicating that teachers are serious about delivering service to the teaching profession in their respective schools.

Level of Teaching Effectiveness

Shown in Table 3 is the level of teaching effectiveness

of public elementary school teachers in Davao del Sur. The overall mean score was 4.38 described as very high. This implies that teaching effectiveness is manifested or felt most of the time. Nonetheless, it can be inferred that teachers have considered teaching as the noblest profession.

Teachers made all the possible efforts to teach their clientele and are highly motivated to accomplish their tasks as teachers. Moreover, it can be gleaned that the school heads make sound decisions and are able to explain them based on professional, ethical and legal principles. Respondents believed that what they are doing in the field are supported by school leaders who manage day to day activities conducive to the formation of trust and confidence to school stakeholders.

Table 3: Level of Teaching Effectiveness

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Having full authority on the subject I am teaching.	0.56	4.45	Very High
Believing that besides my teaching subject. I have the ability to teach other needed subjects like current like current events, general knowledge etc.	0.52	4.59	Very High
Giving due opportunities to the students for proper motivation.	0.47	4.73	Very High
Using more rewards and lesser punishment in the classroom for achievement of desired aims.	0.56	4.66	Very High
I am being well prepared when I come for Teaching.	0.54	4.55	Very High
Keeping friendly and brotherly relationship with my teacher colleagues.	0.57	4.58	Very High
Having respectfully with all guardians without discriminating caste , social status and economics status etc .	0.46	4.69	Very High
Cooperating with the guardian to solve student problems so that they can develop properly given the right opportunities.	0.50	4.63	Very High
Preparing the student to in co-curricular activities according to their abilities and interested.	0.52	4.54	Very High
Preparing lesson plan regularly.	0.53	4.60	Very High
I am being fully conversant with the instructional objectives of the lesson.	0.52	4.44	Very High
Selecting proper teaching aids before hands.	0.52	4.44	Very High
Communicating the subject matter clearly before the students.	0.50	4.49	Very High
Having proper rapport with my students.	0.54	4.45	Very High
Making proper use of the blackboard.	0.65	4.00	High
Giving attention to each student individually.	0.51	4.45	Very High
Developing student's interesting the lesson.	0.52	4.49	Very High
Using needed remedial measure in Teaching.	0.52	4.52	Very High
Controlling the class confidently.	0.66	4.15	High
Having complete knowledge of basis of individual differences.	0.56	4.34	Very High
Always trying to use contemporary educational devices in the Teaching.	0.55	4.29	Very High
Using examples from daily life situations while teaching.	0.53	4.46	Very High
I am being disciplined.	0.53	4.24	Very High
Ensuring that the students understand me when I am teaching.	0.50	4.39	Very High
Overall	0.31	4.38	Very High

Furthermore, it can be inferred that appropriate review, monitoring and evaluation processes is evident most of the time. The school heads play a vital role in maintaining positive teaching effectiveness by monitoring teachers' effectiveness in attaining students learning utilizing varied teaching and learning strategies or approaches.

Correlations between Passion and Commitment

The investigation findings into the connection between commitment and passion are shown in Table 6. The significance level chosen for the link examination was 0.05, which was taken from the hypothesis. The total r-value of.503 and a p-value of less than 0.05 indicated that the null hypothesis should not be accepted. It suggests that there is a substantial connection between a person's passion and their level of commitment. This suggests that a commitment to Teaching is linked to a passion for Teaching. Because the p-value is less than 0.05 and the

overall r-value is.478 on passion criteria,.529 on harmonious passion, and.251 on obsessive passion, the results demonstrate that all indicators of passion have a positive correlation with commitment. This is an exciting finding.

In addition, the data demonstrate that all indicators of commitment have a positive correlation with passion. This is evidenced by the fact that the p-value for each indicator is less than 0.05, and the overall r-value for commitment to students is.220, while the r-value for commitment to teaching is.380, the r-value for commitment to school is.403, and the r-value for commitment to profession is.342.

Correlations between Passion and Teaching Effectiveness

The findings of the test on the association between passion and teaching effectiveness are shown in Table 4. As seen in the table, the indicators of passion are

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Passion and Commitment

Passion	Commitment				Overall
	Commitment to Students	Commitment to Teaching	Commitment to School	Commitment to Profession	
Passion Criteria	.254*(0.000)	.408*(0.000)	.337*(0.000)	.280*(0.000)	.478*(0.000)
Harmonious Passion	.236*(0.000)	.440*(0.000)	.430*(0.000)	.303*(0.000)	.529*(0.000)
Obsessive Pas-sion	.081(0.178)	.138*(0.021)	.221*(0.000)	.230*(0.000)	.251*(0.000)
Overall	.220*(0.000)	.380*(0.000)	.403*(0.000)	.342*(0.000)	.503*(0.000)

positively connected to teaching effectiveness, with an overall r -value of .484 and a p -value of 0.05, indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis. It implies that there is a strong link between passion and teaching effectiveness. Specifically, in the indicator passion criteria, data show a positive correlation with teaching effectiveness because of its computed positive correlation value of .338 or about 34% of its impact on teaching effectiveness with a p -value <0.05 . The p -value result means a positive connection between the passion criteria of passion and

the teaching effectiveness of the respondents; teaching effectiveness needs passion criteria in passion. Also, the other indicator, harmonious passion, has an r -value of .414 or an equivalent of 41%, with a p -value <0.05 . The statistical result shows that harmonious passion is positively associated with teaching effectiveness. Besides, obsessive passion got an r -value of .484 or 48% with a p -value <0.05 , which shows that obsessive passion is needful in teaching effectiveness. In short, identified indicators are helpful tools in attaining teaching effectiveness.

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between Passion and Teaching Effectiveness

Passion	Teaching Effectiveness Overall
Passion Criteria	.338*(0.000)
Harmonious Passion	.414*(0.000)
Obsessive Passion	.366*(0.000)
Overall	.484*(0.000)

Correlations between Teaching Effectiveness and Commitment

The findings of the test on the association between teaching effectiveness and commitment are shown in Table 5. The association was assessed at the 0.05 threshold of significance, as stated in the hypothesis. Data reveal that commitment to students is favorably connected with teaching effectiveness. The r -value is .166, and the p -value are 0.05. The statistical result shows that a commitment to students is a large part of teaching effectiveness. To

be a good teacher, one must be able to set learning goals for their pupils and use successful teaching approaches following trends in education.

Likewise, the other indicator which is commitment to Teaching has an r -value of .216 with a p -value of <0.05 . This shows that commitment to Teaching is positively associated with teaching effectiveness. This implies that teacher's devotion to their work as instructors of learning play a big part in achieving teaching effectiveness.

Also, commitment to school reveals an r -value of .147

Table 6: Significance of the Relationship between Teaching Effectiveness and Commitment

Teaching Effectiveness	Commitment				Overall
	Commitment to Students	Commitment to Teaching	Commitment to School	Commitment to Profession	
Overall	.266*(0.000)	.259*(0.000)	.358*(0.000)	.408*(0.000)	.386*(0.000)

with a p -value of <0.05 . Still, the result is positively correlated to teaching effectiveness. It is safe to assume that commitment to school has an impact in teaching effectiveness. Moreover, commitment to profession has a low positive correlation value of .058 with a p -value of >0.05 but still prove that commitment to profession is significant in teaching effectiveness.

The overall result reflects that teaching effectiveness is positively correlated to commitment having an overall

r -value of .221 with a p -value of <0.05 . Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between teaching effectiveness and commitment is rejected.

On the Mediating Effect of Teaching Effectiveness

Table 7 shows the path analysis on the mediating influence of teaching effectiveness on the link between passion and commitment. The information in this table was gathered

Table 7: Mediating Effect: Path Analysis (No Mediation)

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
PAS--> TE	.379	.484	.041	9.241	***
TE --> COM	-.030	-.030	.061	-.500	.617
PAS --> COM	.415	.518	.047	8.763	***

as a result of conducting AMOS. This table presents the direct effect of passion on teaching effectiveness, teaching effectiveness on commitment, and passion on commitment. Passion and teaching effectiveness is the path a coefficient with an unstandardized regression coefficient of .379, a standardized regression coefficient of .484, SE of .041, and a probability value less than 0.05. Below the significance level of 0.05 implies that these two variables have a significant relationship and a low or small standard error means that the estimate is more precise.

Besides, the effect size or the impact of passion on teaching effectiveness is 38% which completely denies the null hypothesis. Thus, the path b coefficient is teaching effectiveness and commitment, which has an unstandardized regression coefficient of -.030, standardized regression coefficient of -.030, SE of .061, and a p -value greater than 0.05 means that the two variables do not correlate. And lastly, the path c coefficient shows the effect size of passion on commitment. The data result has an unstandardized regression coefficient

of .415 or 42% efficacy rate, a standardized regression coefficient of .518; the computed standard error is .047, and a p-value < 0.05 level of significance. Statistically, this supports the postulation that passion is associated with commitment.

In addition, Figure 3 depicts the result of the mediating effect computation. It shows the effect size of path correlation coefficients of the three variables used in this study. At the 0.05 level, the route analysis gave a p-value of > 0.05, which is insignificant. This suggests that teaching effectiveness does not substantially affect the relationship between passion and commitment among public school elementary teachers. Furthermore, after teaching effectiveness, the mediator variable, the causal association between passion and commitment has been increased from a significant beta coefficient value of .503 to .52, which is still substantial.

X = PASSION (PAS)
 Y = COMMITMENT (COM)
 M = TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS (TE)

Figure 1: Regression Weights on the Mediating Effect of Teaching Effectiveness on the Relationship between Passion and Commitment

Empirically, the raw correlation between passion and commitment has a total impact of .503. The extent of the association between passion and commitment with teaching effectiveness included in the regression is represented by the direct effect value of .52. The indirect effect value of -0.0144 represents the amount of original link between passion and commitment that has been transferred to teaching effectiveness. The formula is: (a*b), where “a” is the path between the independent and mediator variables, “b” denotes the path between the mediator and dependent variables. Moreover, assessed significance of the indirect effect is found to be not significant.

Thus, it is continued to look for the meaning of the indirect effect (c') and the direct effect shows a positive standardized coefficient of .52 which means significant. Therefore, the conclusion is no mediation following the steps of mediation analysis by Zhao et al. (2010). Then, the indirect effect must be divided by the total effect to

get the ratio index; in this case, -0.0144 divided by 0.5056 equals -0.0284. Thus, the final correlation contends that teaching effectiveness carries no influence on the relationship between passion and time. Therefore, the research study falls under no mediation.

Furthermore, there are three stages in mediating study for a third variable to operate as a mediator (Baron & Kenny, 1986). Table 7 categorizes these as Steps 1 through 3. The fourth and last step is Passion, as the independent variable (IV) significantly predicts commitment, the dependent variable, in Step 1 (Path c) (DV). Passion (IV) substantially indicates teaching effectiveness in step 2 (Path a) and the mediator (MV). Teaching effectiveness (MV) strongly signifies commitment in step 3 (Path b) (DV).

Similarly, the goal of steps 1–3 is to prove that there are zero-order correlations between variables. And we can automatically conclude that mediation is not probable with no relationship variables basing the process of estimating the relationship. Furthermore, if there is a significant relationship in steps 1 to 3, one must proceed to step 4. Then in step 4, the combined effect of passion and teaching effectiveness on a commitment is significant. To assess the relevance of the intervening variable, further path analysis of the mediation effect using AMOS SPSS is required.

Furthermore, complete mediation will be attained if the impact of the IV on the DV becomes non-significant at the end of the analysis. It signifies that the mediating variable mediates all of the effects. Only partial mediation is obtained if the regression coefficient is significantly lowered but still significant at the end. It means that while the MV mediates part of the IV, other sections are either direct or mediated by variables not included in the model. In this scenario, the effect of IV (Passion) on DV (commitment) is significantly increased after controlling for MV (teaching effectiveness). Yet, the outcome of the indirect effect value is negative, indicating that no mediation occurred in the final path analysis.

The researcher confirmed that mediation is not essential and that no mediation happens by using Baron and Kenny's steps in testing mediation of teaching efficacy. Firstly, the research conducted a straightforward regression analysis with X predicting M to test for path a- the independent variable, or X (Passion) affects the mediator or M (teaching effectiveness) at the beta coefficient of .38 with a SE of .041, and the relationship is significant at 0.05 significance level. Secondly, the research conducted a straightforward regression analysis with M predicting Y to determine the relevance of path b-the mediating variable or M (teaching effectiveness) affects the dependent variable or D (commitment) at the beta coefficient of -.030, where teaching effectiveness got a residual error of .061.

The relationship is not significant at the 0.05 significance level. It has a p-value of .617, more effective than 0.05. Thirdly, a simple regression analysis was conducted with X predicting Y to test for the significance of

path c- the independent variable or X (Passion) affects the dependent variable or Y (commitment) at the beta coefficient of .415, where commitment has a residual error 2 of .047. The relationship is significant at the 0.05 significance level. Last but not least, after controlling the dependent variable or Y (commitment) as predicted by the independent variable or X (Passion) and including the mediating variable or M (teaching effectiveness) as a predictor of commitment, it is increased to .52. However, the alpha level is still significant at a 0.05 significance level of Passion and commitment, but statistically, no mediation was found in this study.

Since it has no mediation, it could be claimed that teaching effectiveness does not influence the relationship between Passion and commitment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions are drawn. As a result of the study's data, there is significant evidence to accept the null hypothesis in research aim number two. Furthermore, the respondent public school teachers had a high level of passion and devotion and a very high level of teaching effectiveness. The study's outcomes also demonstrate a significant association between passion and commitment in the classroom. Similarly, there is a favorable relationship between passion and teaching effectiveness. Furthermore, there is a substantial relationship between teaching effectiveness and commitment.

Lastly, the study's findings revealed that no mediation of teaching effectiveness exists in the relationship between passion and commitment. Corollary to this, Deci & Ryan's (1985) Self-Determination Theory (SDT) coincides with the findings of passion for which human motivation and personality focus on people's fundamental psychological requirements and growth tendencies. It is concerned with the reasons that drive people's decisions, regardless of whether they are affected or not by others. Self-determination theory is a macro theory of human motivation that is a fundamental component of passion and commitment, leading to effective Teaching.

Several recommendations are made based on the findings and conclusions. Firstly, teachers need to intervene on obsessive passion, which was found to be at the lowest indicator of passion. School administrators may develop an activity that solves teachers' problems related to their difficulties controlling to do the job as a teacher and impresses them that Teaching manages their way of life in school. In this case, schools, especially the school heads, may plan for a load of seminars about teaching arts for their teachers. Motivation is needful for teachers to attain an obsessive feeling for their job.

Secondly, there is a need also for teachers to improve in commitment to school under commitment. A strict agreement with the organization's policies on crucial matters relating to its employee, maintaining a positive school climate and improvement, and strong connectedness of school's values and teachers' values are

needful matters in teaching as teachers. Hence, the leader substantially impacts this exciting topic for the teacher's job to maintain faithfulness in Teaching.

Lastly, there is another issue for teachers to overcome regarding teaching effectiveness questions: "I make proper use of the blackboard." The advent of new instructional materials slowly replaces the old way of presenting and discussing lessons or the traditional method. We now have new methods of Teaching like PowerPoint presentations, laptops, and printers to aid teachers in the discussion. However, the benefit of using blackboards is that they allow you to see handouts, review tests, track progress, and more to improve your students' learning experience. Outside of class, Blackboard allows students to communicate with the instructor and other students. It also allows students to help and collaborate with one another to improve their overall course experience.

Moreover, there are things that teachers may follow effectively in using a blackboard. Legible writing and organization of board work are considerations crucial to effective Teaching. Addendum, teachers do not need to be fast in erasing the words written on a blackboard but give time to students to copy the topic. Teachers do not need to write all the words on the blackboard but only those essential words in the lesson. Thus, students can use the blackboard to present mathematical solutions and write letters of the alphabet.

Undeniably, no mediation of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between passion and commitment was found in this study which can be useful for future studies toward examining other variables that can mediate the relationship between variables. Besides, the research findings in this study, on the other hand, are a credible reference for future researchers and educational administrative systems in Department of Education or DepEd when planning about teaching effectiveness courses and seminars of teachers.

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